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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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COMMUNICATIVE LEARNING AS A BASIS FOR CRITICAL THINKING DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article demonstrates the use of communicative learning, namely linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, and strategic competencies, which form the basis for the development of critical thinking skills. The purpose of this review article is to illustrate the effectiveness of using communicative competencies in teaching and developing critical thinking abilities. Communicative competencies based on the use of innovative pedagogical technologies play a crucial role in the modern process of teaching English. Moreover, communicative learning is an approach to language learning that emphasizes interaction both as a means and as the ultimate goal of learning. Great changes are taking place in pedagogical science today. The traditional system of education does not meet the requirements of modern pedagogy, which emphasizes the importance and necessity of the comprehensive development of each student in the learning process. Therefore, the principles of developmental learning are implemented through the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the higher education system, ensuring the comprehensive development of students' personalities and cognitive abilities.

Key words: communicative learning, communicative competence, linguistic or grammatical competence, pragmatic/discursive competence, sociolinguistic competence, strategic competence, pedagogical technologies, written and communicative skills.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola kommunikativ ta'lim, ya'ni lingvistik, sotsiolingvistik, pragmatik va strategik kompetensiyalardan foydalanishga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, ular tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning asosini tashkil etadi. Mazkur maqolaning maqsadi o'qitish va tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda kommunikativ kompetensiyalardan foydalanish samaradorligini ko'rsatishdan iborat. Zamonaviy ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishga asoslangan kommunikativ kompetensiyalar hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Kommunikativ ta'lim til o'rganishning shunday yondashuviki, unda o'zaro ta'sir o'qitishning ham vositasi, ham yakuniy maqsadi sifatida qaraladi. Bugungi kunda pedagogika fanida katta o'zgarishlar yuz bermoqda. An'anaviy ta'lim tizimi zamonaviy pedagogika talablariga to'liq javob bermaydi, chunki zamonaviy pedagogika o'quv jarayonida har bir o'quvchining har tomonlama rivojlantirishining muhimligi va zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Shu sababli rivojlantiruvchi ta'lim tamoyillari oliy ta'lim tizimida talabalarning shaxsiyati va bilish qobiliyatlarini har tomonlama rivojlantirishni ta'minlaydigan zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash orqali amalga oshiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kommunikativ ta'lim, kommunikativ kompetensiya, lingvistik yoki grammatik kompetensiya, pragmatik/diskursiv kompetensiya, sotsiolingvistik kompetensiya, strategik kompetensiya, pedagogik texnologiyalar, yozma va kommunikativ ko'nikmalar.

Аннотация: Эта статья раскрывает использование коммуникативного обучения на основе лингвистических, социолингвистических, прагматических и стратегических компетенций, которые являются основой для развития навыков критического мышления. Цель данной обзорной научной статьи – проиллюстрировать эффективность использования коммуникативных компетенций в обучении и развитии способностей к критическому мышлению. Коммуникативные компетенции, основанные на использовании инновационных педагогических технологий, играют решающую роль в современном процессе обучения английскому языку. Коммуникативное обучение представляет собой подход к изучению языка, который подчеркивает взаимодействие как средство и как конечную цель обучения. Сегодня в педагогической науке происходят значительные изменения. Традиционная система обучения не отвечает требованиям современной педагогики, которая подчеркивает важность и необходимость всестороннего развития каждого обучающегося в процессе обучения. В связи с этим принципы развивающего обучения реализуются посредством использования современных педагогических технологий в системе высшего образования, обеспечивающих всестороннее развитие личности и познавательных способностей студента.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативное обучение, коммуникативная компетенция, лингвистическая или грамматическая компетенция, прагматическая/дискурсивная компетенция, социолингвистическая компетенция, стратегическая компетенция, педагогические технологии, письменные и коммуникативные навыки.

INTRODUCTION

Communicative learning is a contemporary model of language teaching and, consequently, an effective means of developing critical thinking skills. Communicative competence, which encompasses linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, and strategic competences, plays a pivotal role in the development of critical thinking abilities. The implementation of communicative learning in the educational process can significantly enhance learners' communicative skills and provide a solid foundation for the development of critical thinking. A distinctive feature of modern language teaching methodology is its communicative orientation, aimed at teaching communication and enabling learners to use language in its primary function – communication itself.

Learning a new language becomes easier and more enjoyable when it is meaningful and relevant to learners' needs. Communicative language teaching is an approach to second and foreign language instruction that emphasizes interaction both as a means and as the ultimate goal of language learning. It is also known as the “communicative approach to foreign language teaching” or simply the “communicative approach”. Through this approach, students engage with authentic materials and develop their language skills through interaction with peers and teachers. Human communication fulfills numerous goals at both personal and social levels. People communicate information, ideas, and beliefs; express emotions and relationships; and establish and maintain their positions within various social contexts by using appropriate language forms and speech patterns that promote solidarity, harmony, and cooperation or express disagreement and dissatisfaction. Communication-oriented instruction aims to develop learners' ability to communicate effectively in a foreign language by employing a variety of tasks and techniques. Therefore, the goal of foreign language teaching is not merely to master its linguistic system but to acquire communicative competence and perform speech actions in the target language. The significance of speech communication extends far beyond the simple exchange of information. Speech developed simultaneously with human consciousness and serves to materialize thought, transforming individual consciousness into a social phenomenon and individual information into public knowledge shared by society. The aim of this article is to characterize the effectiveness of using communicative competences in the teaching process, particularly for the development of critical thinking abilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Critical thinking skills are closely associated with communicative competences. Therefore, examining each competence is essential for understanding their contribution to critical thinking development. Communicative competence refers to a language user's knowledge and ability to communicate appropriately according to cultural traditions, generally accepted rules, and social norms. It involves the ability to understand and convey meaning effectively within a social context. Communicative competence consists of four interrelated components: linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic (discursive), and strategic competence. Linguistic or grammatical competence refers to the ability to apply grammatical, lexical, syntactic, and stylistic rules in spoken and written communication. This competence is important because it explains how utterances and sentences are structured, providing the formal basis of language. However, linguistic knowledge alone is insufficient for achieving communicative goals, as non-linguistic factors also contribute to the construction of social meaning.

Linguistic competence encompasses both conscious and unconscious knowledge of language, including sentence structures, morphological forms, lexical resources, and phonological or orthographic systems. In Uzbekistan, linguistic competence has traditionally been taught within the framework of Saussurean linguistics, with considerable attention devoted to form, structure, and semantic meaning. This approach often prioritizes rules over practice, assuming that knowledge of grammatical rules guarantees successful communication. However, contemporary language education emphasizes that grammar instruction should not be static, isolated, or monotonous. When grammatical structures are taught within meaningful discourse and language-awareness contexts, learning becomes more effective, engaging, and sustainable.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Pragmatic (discursive) competence is the ability to interpret and convey meaning appropriately within a specific context. Understanding meaning depends on factors such as time, place, and social circumstances. During communication, individuals exchange not only information and semantic content but also intentions. Every utterance reflects the speaker's intentions, which are shaped by contextual factors. The ability to interpret and respond to these intentions constitutes pragmatic competence. Pragmatics studies the context in which communication occurs as well as the intentions of language users. It also examines how listeners and readers infer meaning beyond what is explicitly stated to arrive at the intended interpretation. Pragmatic competence

should be systematically developed in foreign language classrooms because it enhances students' ability to interpret meanings in authentic social situations. Interactive classroom activities should focus on concepts such as cooperation, contextual understanding, and meaning negotiation, thereby strengthening learners' pragmatic competence. Sociolinguistic competence refers to awareness of how culture, social norms, traditions, and social variables influence language use. It involves understanding how different cultures employ grammar, syntax, semantics, and stylistic features to describe similar objects, events, and processes. This competence also enables learners to use language appropriately in social contexts. As noted by scholars in communicative language teaching, learners should acquire not only grammatically correct sentences but also socially appropriate ways of communicating. Effective communication requires understanding when to speak, what to say, and how to adapt language to specific situations. Without knowledge of social rules governing language use, grammatical competence alone becomes insufficient.

Sociolinguistic competence further encompasses an understanding of how factors such as gender, age, social status, ideology, and cultural background shape the interpretation and expression of meaning. Different cultures often interpret the same objects and processes differently because they are grounded in distinct systems of shared knowledge and experience. Each culture possesses common practices, experiences, rules, and norms that collectively form what may be called shared knowledge. Such knowledge develops through the accumulated experiences of community members and plays a crucial role in interpreting social reality. Even when individuals speak the same language and produce grammatically correct utterances, communication may fail if they do not share the same cultural references and background knowledge. Myths, proverbs, songs, poems, fairy tales, and various forms of literature all embody cultural knowledge that is activated through language.

Different cultures therefore attribute different meanings to similar social phenomena. For example, within the cultural context of Uzbekistan, university instructors often establish authority and classroom control at the beginning of a lesson, whereas in the United States greater emphasis is placed on facilitating learning and ensuring access to information. Through communication, individuals continuously reproduce and reinforce cultural distinctions. It is within these shared practices and bodies of knowledge that language users acquire social roles, identities, and significance. Consequently, sociolinguistic competence examines how cultural knowledge and social practices influence what people consider appropriate or acceptable to say in specific situations. What is regarded as appropriate in one cultural setting may be considered inappropriate in another. Strategic competence refers to the ability to overcome deficiencies in linguistic, sociolinguistic, or pragmatic knowledge by employing alternative communication strategies. It enables language users to maintain effective communication despite gaps in their language proficiency. Authentic situations such as telephone conversations and job interviews often present challenges for language learners who rely solely on grammatical knowledge. For instance, during an interview, a learner may encounter unfamiliar vocabulary or questions. Rather than simply stating that they do not understand, strategically competent learners employ paraphrasing, clarification requests, or other communicative strategies to maintain interaction effectively. Therefore, strategic competence involves recognizing limitations in one's linguistic, pragmatic, or sociolinguistic knowledge and compensating for these limitations to achieve successful communication. The implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies increasingly relies on the development of communicative competences, which constitute a fundamental basis for the evolution of critical thinking skills.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Currently, the use of communicative learning can significantly enhance the educational process through modern technologies aimed at developing critical thinking skills. Moreover, there is a growing need to employ innovative technologies to update the methodology of English language teaching. In pedagogical science and practice, various interpretations of pedagogical technology can be identified. This diversity is not accidental, as each author approaches the understanding of technology from a particular theoretical and methodological perspective. However, all existing approaches share the following common characteristics: ω pedagogical technology is purposefully developed on the basis of a specific pedagogical idea and is grounded in the author's methodological and philosophical position; ω the sequence of technological actions and operations is constructed in strict accordance with tasks formulated as specific expected outcomes; ω the functioning of pedagogical technology involves the interrelated activities of teachers and students, taking into account the principles of individualization and differentiation, the optimal use of human and technical resources, as well as dialogue and communication; ω step-by-step planning and consistent implementation of pedagogical technology elements should be carried out by the teacher, ensuring the achievement of the intended learning outcomes by all students.

The formation of competence is based on a learner-centered and activity-based approach to education. In this context, competence is regarded as “an integral characteristic of an individual that serves as a potential foundation for successful performance, enabling a person to adequately assess and reassess difficulties arising during problem-solving and to identify non-standard ways of achieving goals.” Competence is manifested through activity. Therefore, as S. B. Seryakova notes, it can be assessed only through practical activity. Consequently, teachers face the challenge of revising instructional technologies in order to move beyond the simple transmission of information and knowledge toward contextual learning, which involves solving practical problems, gaining experience in selecting appropriate tools independently, and determining effective algorithms for their application. “Thinking is an effective way to refine our assessment skills to the point where we feel confident in our own ability to determine what ‘works’ in our classes. Its effectiveness increases when it is evaluated critically.” According to Ladyzhenskaya, communicative competence is “the most important professional skill of a teacher, requiring not only knowledge of language norms at the level of native speakers but also the ability to speak expressively. A teacher’s speech should serve as a model for students.”

Students often experience difficulties when communicating on specific topics. Therefore, the development of communicative competence can enhance learners’ motivation and increase the effectiveness of English language instruction. In particular, students’ oral statements frequently lack coherence and logical consistency. They do not always consider the communicative situation, encounter difficulties in expressing their own opinions, and struggle to formulate and justify their viewpoints. Their speech is often slow and characterized by unnecessary pauses. In addition, limited vocabulary is frequently observed, and professional terminology is either omitted or replaced by paraphrased expressions. Today, economically developed countries are compelled to train specialists capable of applying theoretical knowledge in practice, utilizing innovative technologies for the development of critical thinking skills, and actively participating in professional communication at both regional and international levels. Consequently, proficiency in foreign languages has become an essential means of communication and an effective tool for obtaining technical and technological information necessary for language learning and teaching. Working with modern technologies designed to foster critical thinking is one of the key competencies of English language specialists, while knowledge of communication strategies in visual-receptive activities contributes significantly to the successful accomplishment of communicative tasks.

CONCLUSION

The above discussion allows us to conclude that communicative learning, based on innovative pedagogical technologies for developing critical thinking skills, creates appropriate conditions for mastering foreign language teaching and provides favorable opportunities for the development of future teachers as culturally and linguistically competent individuals possessing highly developed communicative and intercultural skills for solving communicative problems. The task of modern methodology is to enhance teachers’ competence in the field of highly effective communication and interactive technologies, to create and develop a universal educational environment, and to stimulate the formation of critical thinking skills.

Therefore, the following communicative competences can be distinguished: Linguistic or grammatical competence; Pragmatic/discursive competence; Sociolinguistic competence; Strategic competence. Communicative competences are related to a person’s ability to take responsibility, participate in joint decision-making processes, and enhance learners’ critical thinking abilities. These competences determine learners’ mastery of written and oral communication skills, which are particularly important in modern life and professional activities. Communicative learning is associated with the emergence of an information-oriented innovative society, in which the mastery of modern pedagogical technologies is of particular importance. The use of contemporary pedagogical technologies in higher education institutions creates new opportunities for implementing the didactic principles of individualization and differentiation of instruction. It positively influences the development of students’ cognitive activity, creativity, and consciousness, while facilitating the transition from teacher-centered instruction to self-education. Communicative learning, as a source of critical thinking development, adds ingenuity, creativity, and flexibility to English language classes.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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